

Analysis of Refueling of Individual Fuel Assemblies in the Reactor during One Fuel Campaign

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Models for initial and stationary fuel loads for VVER-1200 have been developed to perform calculations for meeting acceptance criteria when replacing partially burnt fuel assemblies with fresh ones during the campaign. The article presents calculations of the core neutron-physical characteristics and assesses compliance with acceptance criteria during the replacement of a partially burnt-out fuel assembly with a new one at various time points throughout a fuel campaign at the VVER-1200 nuclear power plant.

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1. Introduction

Safety assessment in nuclear engineering often relies on the use of engineering codes like DYN3D [1]. To perform these assessments, constant libraries in appropriate formats need to be generated. Two fundamentally different approaches are available for such calculations: employing various approximations (formulated format) and directly computing all cross-sections for all states (tabulated format). The formulated format is more flexible and requires fewer states to be created, while the tabulated format is generally more accurate but demands several orders of magnitude more states to establish a correctly functioning library.

Currently, accident analysis is conducted using a conservative approach, where the necessary degree of conservatism is achieved by selecting appropriate initial and boundary conditions to ensure the consideration of the most severe scenario of the analyzed accident.

The replacement of some fuel assemblies in the reactor during one fuel campaign is a possible event resulting from a violation of

operating conditions or damage to fuel assemblies during fuel refueling or other accidents. Such a replacement is possible during the operation of the reactor due to the specifics of nuclear power plants (NPPs). Despite the failure of one fuel assembly, continued operation is necessary to achieve economic goals. This study is aimed at studying the potential problems that arise when partially burned fuel assemblies are replaced with fresh fuel assemblies during a fuel campaign.

In this stage of the research, VVER-1200 models [2–6] for initial and stationary fuel loads [7, 8] were developed using DYN3D for a conservative assessment of the event involving the replacement of partially burnt fuel assemblies with fresh ones. Additionally, test calculations were performed in the specified states to obtain preliminary data for further analysis of the investigated event.

2. Modeling partially burnt fuel assembly replacement in DYN3D and safety analysis for VVER-1200 reactors

The replacement of partially burnt fuel assemblies with fresh ones due to operational damage or reactor power reduction is a crucial

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event in the operation of VVER-1200 reactors. To conduct safety assessments of neutron-physical characteristics (NFC) with conservative estimates, parameters representing the partially burnt active zone needed to be defined. Two VVER-1200 models were created in DYN3D for stationary and initial fuel loads to examine the impact of replacing partially burnt fuel assemblies with fresh ones. We use in our calculations the library of constants in formulated format for the DYN3D code, obtained earlier using the Monte Carlo code SERPENT [9, 10]

DYN3D provides flexible capabilities to construct a reactor's core model. The core is represented by hexagonal prisms with dimensions typical of fuel assemblies in VVER reactors. The axial step size was set to 20 to balance accuracy and computational cost. Given the asymmetrical changes in energy release during most accident scenarios involving positive reactivity insertion in VVER-1200 reactors, a full-scale model with 360° symmetry was developed for the computational analysis.

To enhance the modeling of neutron leakage beyond the active zone, two additional peripheral hexagonal cell rows were introduced as radial reflectors, along with upper and lower axial reflector layers. The outer boundaries were treated with black boundary conditions.

The calculations were conducted to assess the state of all fuel assemblies at the middle of the operational campaign for both initial and stationary fuel loads. It is assumed that the neutronic properties of newly loaded fuel assemblies correspond to their design data, and any errors in fuel pellet enrichment, uranium-235 content, or positioning within the assemblies have been identified during the fuel manufacturing stage. The planned fuel assembly arrangement for the upcoming campaign is determined by preliminary calculations using certified codes and described in relevant regulatory documents. Deviations from the planned arrangement may lead to unanticipated redistributions of neutron flux density and energy release within the reactor's active zone, potentially compromising

the reactor's safety during power operation.

After refueling and standard procedures, the reactor is brought to critical state and then powered up. To prevent any deterioration in thermal-hydraulic parameters due to incorrect fuel assembly positioning, timely identification of misplaced fuel assemblies is critical. Therefore, when the reactor power exceeds 30% of nominal, control over the energy release distribution within the fuel assemblies is conducted based on experimental data from Instrumentation and Control Systems for Nuclear Power Plants (I&C Systems).

The accident scenario bears similarities to an accident of an operator's mistake during fuel loading. Thus, similar safety assessment criteria and potential threats are applied in this situation.

3. Replacement model for a partially burnt fuel assembly in DYN3D

In performing the calculations for Nuclear Fuel Handling (NFH), control is exercised over the following parameters:

- non-uniform distribution of energy release within the Fuel Assembly Zone, denoted as (K_q) ;
- relative power of the most power-intensive fuel rod in the Fuel Assembly, denoted as (K_r) ;
- margin to the onset of heat exchange crisis, departure-from-nucleate-boiling (DNBR), within the Fuel Assembly.

We introduce additional indexes i, j for these variable so that i ($i = 1 \dots, 163$) is a fuel-assembly number in a j -th axial layer, ($j = 1, \dots, 20$). The following constraints (1)–(3) must be satisfied:

FIG. 1. (Color online) An energy release distribution for the initial loading (a) and for the steady-state loading (b), 160th day of the campaign.

$$(K_q)_{i,j} \leq (K_q)_{i,j}^{Perm}(W), \quad (1)$$

$$(K_r)_{i,j} \leq (K_r)_{i,j}^{Perm}(W), \quad (2)$$

$$DNBR_{i,j} \geq 1.00 \quad (3)$$

where W is a reactor power; $(K_q)_{i,j}^{Perm}(W)$ is a permissible value of the power non-uniformity coefficient in the i -th Fuel Assembly of the j -th axial layer at the power level W . The permissible margin to the onset of heat exchange crisis, $(DNBR)_{i,j}$ for i -th Fuel Assembly in j -th axial layer at power level W .

The values $(K_q)_{i,j}^{Perm}(W)$ and $(K_r)_{i,j}^{Perm}(W)$ are calculated separately for each loading and must ensure compliance with the constraints on linear fuel and cladding power considering non-uniformity of energy release within the Fuel Assembly, mechanical deviations in the energy release of the Fuel Assemblies, reactor power accuracy, and experimental error in determining fuel power. Constraints (1)–(3) result from limitations on the maximum values of fuel and cladding power.

$(DNBR)_{i,j}$ is calculated using the OKB-2 method for the hot fuel rod. Possible errors in critical heat flux value, engineering safety factor, and accuracy in reactor power determination are taken into account. For VVER-1200 reactor type $K_q^{Perm} = 1.40$, $K_r^{Perm} = 1.57$, anything above considered as incident for safety assessment measures. For $DNBR^{Perm} = 1.35$ anything below considered as incident for safety assessment measures.

Violation of any of the constraints (1)–(3) during power increase in accordance with the regulations leads to a halt in power escalation and reduction of power level to the permissible value. Subsequently, an analysis of the reasons leading to constraint violation is performed. One of the hypotheses is incorrect fuel assembly loading, which can be verified by comparing calculated and experimental energy release distributions in the steady-state reactor conditions and conducting additional experiments to determine the weight of individual Control and Safety Rods (CSR) to compare with their calculated values. During the control of compliance with the constraints (1)–

Table 1: Main Initial Conditions for the Core.

Parameter	Value
Nominal Thermal Power of the Reactor, MW	3200
Coolant Flow Rate through the Reactor (at the inlet temperature), m^3/h	88000 (-3000, +2100)
Coolant Pressure at the Reactor Outlet, absolute, MPa	16.2 ± 0.3
Coolant Temperature at the Reactor Inlet, $^{\circ}C$	298.2 (+2, -4)
Coolant Temperature at the Reactor Outlet, $^{\circ}C$	328.6 ± 5
Number of Loops, units	4
Number of Fuel Assemblies in the Core, units	163
Number of Fuel Assemblies with Control and Safety Rods, units	121
Calculated First Circuit Pressure, MPa	17.64
Calculated Temperature at the First Circuit Inlet, $^{\circ}C$	298
Calculated Temperature at the First Circuit Outlet,	328
Boric Acid Concentration, g/kg	Equilibrium
Average Prompt Neutron Lifetime (minimum), μs	16.0
Time for Control Rods to Drop to Fast Reactor Shutdown Signal, s	4
Initial Position of the 12th Group of Control Rods, %	90
Initial Position of Other Groups of Control Rods, %	100

Table 2: Controlled Parameters.

NPhC	160th day Initial loading	240th day Initial loading	300th day Initial loading	160th day Steady-state loading	240th day Steady-state loading	300th day Steady-state loading
K_q	1.3945	1.4310	1.4894	1.4813	1.5950	1.7069
K_r	1.6959	1.7120	1.7498	1.7871	1.9677	2.1879
Coolant Temperature, $^{\circ}C$	339.10	341.71	343.09	342.91	344.60	346.87
Fuel Temperature, $^{\circ}C$	1054.6	1062.7	1072.8	1096.4	1171.6	1278.6
DNBR by OKB-2	1.33	1.31	1.29	1.29	1.25	1.21

(3) during reactor startup, the most dangerous errors in fuel assembly loading can be identified. However, this control is not sufficient to detect certain critical errors in fuel assembly loading.

Table 1 presents the input parameters for the calculations.

4. Calculation results

The results of test calculations for the non-uniformity parameter K_q are presented for the initial loading conditions in Figs. 1a, 2a, and 3a and for the steady-state loading conditions

in Figs. 1b, 2b, and 3b. The different positions for the most power-intensive Fuel Assembly were selected for the initial and steady-state loadings. For the initial loading, it was Fuel Assembly of type Z33Z9 with an enrichment of 3.3% and Control and Safety Rods (CSR), located near the core center. For the steady-state loading, it was Fuel Assembly of type Z49A2 with CSR, positioned at a peripheral layer of the core. In both cases, these Fuel Assemblies had the highest energy release. Table 2 represents safety parameters for each state.

The obtained results show that in most cases described in this study, the replacement

FIG. 2. (Color online) An energy release distribution for the initial loading (a) and the steady-state loading (b), 240th day of the campaign.

of the partially burnt Fuel Assembly with a fresh one without changing the loading pattern significantly violates the parameter K_q , indicating non-uniform energy release. This non-uniformity is of a local nature, and except for K_r , the other

FIG. 3. (Color online) An energy release distribution for the initial loading (a) and for the steady-state loading (b), 300th day of the campaign.

values do not exceed permissible limits. Thus, the replacement can lead to operational conditions violation, which may result in accidents but is not considered critical by itself. It is also important to note that the calculations of the

coolant temperatures for the considered states are close to the saturation state (saturated steam), making them insufficiently accurate for most cases, requiring additional calculations using CFD codes.

5. Conclusions

The following results have been obtained from this study.

Acceptance criteria have been established for conducting calculations of the main neutron-physical parameters for VVER-1200 during the replacement of partially burnt fuel assemblies with new ones.

VVER-1200 models for both initial and steady-state core loadings have been developed for the mid-campaign conditions using Serpent

and DYN3D codes. These models enable the calculation of neutron-physical characteristics affecting safety during the replacement of partially burnt fuel assemblies with fresh ones at various campaign stages.

Test calculations have been performed, and the results of energy release distribution have been obtained for the replacement of the most power-intensive fuel assemblies with fresh ones. The obtained results indicate that in some cases, towards the end of the campaign, the value of K_g exceeds the permissible limit. K_r exceeds its limit for all cases. The $DNBR$ according to the OKB-2 method is 1.21 in the worst case for the steady-state loading and 1.29 for the initial loading. The fuel and coolant temperatures, as well as enthalpy, are within acceptable limits.

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